

Enhancing Border Checks with Blockchain towards Self-Sovereign Identity

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Abstract

Research question – Since the mid-2000s, the digitalisation of border checks has often referred to the increased adoption of automated border control (ABC) at border crossing points in all border environments from airports and seaports to land border crossings. Key prerequisites for the operational implementations of the so-called eGates have been the electronic machine-readable travel document together with biometric technologies that have facilitated the automation of much of the tasks performed by border guards at manual control booths for selected groups of nationalities. Now, the next wave of major changes is emerging with the development of electronic identification (eID), with certain implementations particularly designed for cross-border use cases. An example of this is the Digital Traveller Credential (DTC), initiated and forwarded by the New Technologies Working Group (NTWG) of the International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO). The evolution of eID strongly aligns with the increased demands for data privacy to ensure that individuals can better control how much information is shared about themselves, with whom and for what purpose. A key concept relating to these developments is Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) which provides individuals control of their digital identity, creating user autonomy. SSIs are perceived as the next generation of digital identities across open networks enabling cross-border identification while complying with existing and shortly revised regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the electronic IDentification, Authentication and trust Services (eIDAS). In this paper, we investigate and present a practical implementation of the SSI concept in the context of European external border checks. One possible technology to provide the so-called data self-sovereignty is Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), including blockchains.

Research methodology – This paper reports a technical solution that utilizes SSI concept in the border checks context, implemented with blockchain technology and verifiable credentials. DLT and blockchains are well-suited for implementing SSI systems, as they support distributed architecture solutions and fault-tolerant consensus mechanisms facilitating the achievement of digital trust between different parties. DLT is developed for instance by the Linux foundation dispensing several distributed ledger projects and associated solutions for digital identity and self-sovereign identity. One of these projects is the Hyperledger Indy (Indy), and our implementation is based on it. Together with decentralized identities, Indy provides verifiable claims that are an interoperable format for exchanging digital identity attributes and relationships. The format is in the standardization pipeline of the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). The claims use Zero Knowledge Proofs (ZKP) to confirm that the data in a set of claims is partially or fully true without revealing any additional information, including the identity of the prover. The ZKP offers a framework according to which the disclosure of information during claim verification process can be managed.

Data used – The operational architecture model of Indy is based on Verifiable Credentials Data Model (VCDM). Three different actors are included in the model: issuer, holder and verifier. Our implemented use cases (UC) relate to 1) the checking of traveller's digital identity, and 2) the checking of travel inspection history. In UC-1, the border control authority confirms the validity of the digital identity with the help of the ledger and approves/denies border crossing, thus making the authority the *verifier* as according to the VCDM model. In comparison, the traveller is the *holder* of the credentials related to his/her digital identity, while the *issuer* is represented by an authority that issues the credentials of the digital identity, such as the national police. Similar to UC-1, the border authority acts as the *verifier* in UC-2. The *holder* is instead a governmental body storing records relating to the checks, while the *issuers* are border crossing points that have previously performed the travel document verification procedure and sent the checking result as a record with credentials to the government

wallet. In the proof-of-concept implementation, no genuine data of travellers are used. Instead, the solution resorts to simulated data for exhibiting that the solution is functional.

Key findings – Basic functionality was straightforward to achieve with the Indy SDK repository and tools for the UC-1 and UC-2. This included setting up a test network of Indy nodes, and the creation of Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs), private encrypted storage files (i.e. wallets), credential schemas and credential definitions. Credential issuance and credential verification were also built in. It was observed however, that beyond the basic functionality, the Indy development support was less thorough and available mostly in a scattered form across various websites. The availability of all described features was also unclear, and it was difficult to distinguish whether the features are already implemented in Indy's current version or only part of Indy's future development plans. In creating more sophisticated solutions for use cases with greater complexity, these issues common to any open-source resources may pose an implementation challenge. Also, large scale utilization of blockchain technology requires more comprehensive blockchain infrastructure in terms of co-operation between countries and the related actors.

According to self-sovereign data principles, the disclosure of personal data should not exceed what is absolutely required according to relevant regulations. In our solution based on verifiable credentials, the amount of personal data could be limited or even completely hidden if compared to the state of the art. Essentially, the system only needs to confirm a successful authorization process. Additionally, a high level of trust towards the system should be established from border authority's perspective. In future work, more emphasis should be placed on in-depth user training consisting of dedicated training materials and test environments to enhance the solution's understandability to users, as decentralized systems or the blockchain technology itself still are somewhat unfamiliar in the border security context. Border guards need a sufficient overview of the mechanisms and techniques upon which the blockchain solutions are built. High processing speed (potentially less than 1 second) makes any manual overseeing of individual phases impractical and vain also from the travellers' perspective. Regarding automation level, it is possible that almost a fully automated border control process is enabled in the future. This raises important questions on the human role in the overall process.

Key words – Border Security, Self-Sovereign Identity, Distributed-Ledger Technology, Blockchain Technology, Hyperledger Indy

Paper type – Extended abstract

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